

THE ROLE OF INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS IN THE EMOTIONAL FORMATION OF PUPILS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10381687>

Abstract. *This article focuses on the development of biological factors, as well as social psychological aspects of students under the influence of constant external stimuli, and the role of interpersonal relationships in the process of formation of students' emotional sphere and sociability.*

Keywords: *communication, impressionability, emotional states, behavioral changes.*

Introduction. Physical and speech development of the child is accompanied by changes in the emotional sphere. His views on the world and his relationships with others are changing. A child's ability to recognize and control emotions is enhanced by understanding behavior, for example, where adult opinions about "bad" and "good" behavior are important. Adults should have a good idea of what to expect from children, otherwise there will be incorrect calculations that do not take into account the characteristics of the child's age. The ideal attitude of an adult to a child is gradual adaptation to the emotional development and formation of the child's personality. By the age of three, the child's emotional development reaches such a level that he can behave in an exemplary manner. Just because kids are capable of "good" behavior doesn't mean they always will.

It is not uncommon for children to show displeasure in the form of tears, tantrums and screams. Although the older ones are not as angry as the younger ones, they have a strong sense of self and independence. If a four-year-old child argues using speech in an argument, he does not necessarily become hysterical. But if adults do not answer the child's question: "Why should I?" - then a breakdown may occur. If a four-year-old has had a very tired or stressful day, his behavior will be similar to that of a younger child. This is a signal to adults that the child has accumulated too much to bear at the moment. He needs love, comfort and a chance to act younger for a while.

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The development of emotions and feelings in preschool children depends on a number of conditions. Emotions and feelings are formed in the process of communication by the child's peers. Individual aspects of the psyche of children of different ages are not equally sensitive to educational conditions. The younger the child and the greater his vulnerability, the more important is his dependence on the conditions in which he was brought up. Inadequate emotional connections can lead to a delay in emotional development that can last a lifetime.

The teacher should strive to establish close emotional ties with each child. Relationships with other people, their actions are the most important source of emotions of a preschool child: joy, tenderness, sympathy, anger, anxiety and other experiences. Feelings that arise in a child towards other people are easily transferred to fictional characters - fairy tales, stories. Experiments can also appear in connection with animals, toys, plants. A child, for example, sympathizes with a broken flower. Miscommunication in the family can lead to: One-sided attachment, often to the mother. At the same time, the need to communicate with peers weakens; Jealousy when the second child appears in the family, if the first child feels left out; Fear when adults express frustration at the slightest excuse to threaten a child. And excitement can arise in an unusual situation. The child may develop fear. For example, fear of the dark. If a child is afraid of the dark, the darkness itself will scare him.

With specially organized activities (for example, music lessons), children learn to experience certain emotions related to perception (for example, music). Emotions and feelings develop very intensively in the type of activity appropriate to the age of preschool children - a game saturated with experiences. In the process of performing joint labor activities (cleaning the site, a group of rooms), the emotional unity of a group of preschool children develops. Depending on the current situation, any qualitatively different emotions and feelings (love, hate, joy, anger, anxiety) can be positive, negative, indicative. In general, children are optimistic about life situations. They have a cheerful, cheerful mood.

Usually, the feelings and emotions of preschool children are accompanied by expressive actions: facial expressions, pantomime, vocal reactions. Expressive actions are one of the means of communication. The development of feelings and emotions is related to the development of other mental processes and, to the greatest extent, speech. You should always pay special attention to the condition of children, their mood. You can ask, for example, if they had anything interesting, funny, who was happy about what today, who was sad about something, and who cried and why. If the children do not know what to answer, you need to help - remember some funny episode or children's quarrel, ask why it happened, if the children forgave each other. When such conversations become normal, the children themselves put aside various episodes in their memories and talk about them willingly. And that's why children's worries are low.

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It is inappropriate to study and give certain conclusions and recommendations without studying the biological factors and social psychological aspects in the process of formation of the emotional sphere and sociability of adolescent students and without conducting a certain research stage. Because a teenager develops under the influence of constant external stimuli. These stimuli can even cause age-related developmental delays. In developed foreign countries, the correct formation of the communication process of the child from an early age is being studied along with cognitive development, almost based on the territorial demographic growth and the mentality and culture of the society. Pedagogical and psychological activities are carried out in cooperation with psychological centers dealing with parent-child relations and school institutions based on a specific program. We can see in several scientific sources that the intended goals are being achieved as a result of this activity. We should attach importance to the educational, psychological and pedagogical activity of the family, which is the main social environment, and general secondary education schools. Therefore, conducting psychological work aimed at the formation of children's communication along with family and school education, important social-emotional skills that children should acquire during this period, later academic development, we can achieve the correct formation of communication skills.

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